

www.bjisrd.com

Social and Psychological Reasons for Family Divorce in Uzbekistan

Umarov Bakhriddin Mengboevich,

Professor of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology of the Alfraganu University, Doctor of Psychology, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

***Abstract:** In this article discussed about social and psychological reasons for family divorce in Uzbekistan and given some important facts about it.*

***Key words:** social, psychological reasons, divorce, strength, family divorce, collapse, spouse.*

Introduction. Family life develops differently in different people. Not all families are able to withstand the test of strength. Many family functions are disrupted over time, psychological attitudes of spouses to preserve the marriage undergo significant changes, life plans collapse. Therefore, in some cases, it is not only impossible, but also inappropriate to preserve a marriage as a union that does not bring satisfaction to partners. Often, there is only one way out in such a situation - divorce.

A happy marriage based on love and mutual understanding is, of course, good. And divorce? Some consider it evil, while others - deliverance from evil. And it is like rain: when necessary - good, in all other cases - evil, and not a small one. Perhaps, this metaphor most clearly captures the psychological essence of divorce. For some, it is the only way out of a conflict situation in the family, when the presence of another person causes acute irritation, even hatred, and for others, it is a strong emotional and mental shock, leaving a bitter mark on the soul.

According to the statistics agency of Uzbekistan, 4 to 5 percent of those getting divorced are those who have been married for up to one year, and 40 percent are those who have lived in the family for up to five years. While the number of divorces increased by 41% in 2021 and 22% in 2022, the growth rate fell sharply in 2023, increasing by only 0.8% compared to 2022 (the growth rate decreased by 27 times compared to 2022). At the same time, according to the Interstate Statistical Committee of the CIS, Uzbekistan ranks first in the CIS in the number of marriages and last in the number of divorces. In 2022, the number of marriages in Uzbekistan was 8.4 per 1000 people, divorces - 1.4. In 2023, the number of marriages was 283.8 thousand, and divorces were 49.2 thousand.

Discussion. What are the reasons for such a number of divorces, which is not typical for Uzbekistan before? Could they have been avoided? In order to understand these questions and, if possible, answer them, the Institute of Family and Gender Studies of the Republic of Uzbekistan conducted a large-scale survey in Uzbekistan.

Those who had divorced in the last three years were interviewed. And what was revealed? The first place among the reasons for divorce is the lack of mutual understanding and constant conflicts between spouses (22.5%), followed by infertility (15.6%), intrusive interference of the spouses' relatives in the life of the newlyweds (15%) and alcoholism (11%). And such seemingly negative factors as violence and chronic illness of the spouse scored only 4.0% and 4.6% of the total number of reasons for divorce. Conflicts and misunderstanding are the leaders. This is in the first years of marriage. What is it, the inability to live together?

Here is what the experts of the Family Center say: if we do not count such factors as infertility and imprisonment, the main reason for divorce is the elementary ignorance of the new couple about the basics of family life and the spouses living together with relatives (in total, 40% of divorces). 45.9% of respondents believe that their family could have been saved if the spouse's relatives had not interfered in their lives or if they had had the opportunity to live separately. Local government officials say the same, emphasizing that their efforts to reconcile families are reduced to zero due to the uncompromising and often inadequate position of the spouses' older relatives. Why do parents and other older relatives act this way, especially in relation to their daughter-in-law? Out of malice, deliberately? But then, why was it necessary to create a new family, have a lavish wedding, wish the newlyweds happiness for life? Everything that the elders do is based on their life experience, on what they themselves have been through. It's just that times have changed. If earlier, in a traditional family, daughters-in-law tolerated ("we tolerated it and you tolerate it"), today they do not want to tolerate it. "The rebellion of daughters-in-law" is a conflict of values of different generations. The result is divorce.

According to the results of the study, 14.5% of divorces have an economic background. An attempt to understand it leads to the following conclusion: economic troubles in many families begin from the very beginning of their existence - it's all about the family's debts due to the unbearable costs of holding a wedding. So that it is not worse than others (everyone remembers how "Mahalla Duv-Duv Gap" ends)! The young family and the parents of the newlyweds initially become hostages of a luxurious wedding. And more than one family has broken up, faced with its consequences.

15.6% of divorces occur due to the absence of children. A reason to think. Childless spouses often do not even undergo the necessary examination and subsequent treatment, but simply get divorced. Moreover, in most cases, the woman is to blame, although a fairly significant percentage of the infertility problem is rooted in men, and this is a proven medical fact. In many cases, modern medicine is able to solve this problem. Why does society, including its authorized representatives and bodies responsible for solving such problems, treat this indifferently, without really trying to help people? So what is the main reason for divorce? It is no secret that the problem of unpreparedness for marriage is in entering into it too early, when the spouses are 18-20 years old. But those who have experienced divorce do not consider their age to be the reason for divorce. 73% of respondents consider the optimal age for marriage to be up to 22 years, and for guys - 24-25 years (63%). And are young spouses ready to create a family, if they treat this responsibly and take into account all the risks of such a family, which include many aspects - economic, psychological, physiological, etc. And what is being done to prepare young people for marriage?

Sporadic work to strengthen the family is not effective today. Among such organizations as the Women's Committee, the Youth Union, health and education authorities, etc., there is no real, clear division of responsibility for carrying out specific work. There is no understanding of the goals. There is insufficient provision of information materials intended for those who are entering into marriage for the first time. The materials themselves, written in bookish language and filled with outdated moralizing admonitions of a general nature, do not carry any practical value. And of course, no one reads them. And their authors cannot understand what century they live in.

If we talk about direct assistance, here everything is even worse: more than 45% of the divorced respondents reported that they did not receive any help from these organizations. About 40% of the same divorced people with whom the organizations carried out work to preserve families, indicated that everything was limited to a conversation with the spouses and their relatives. And the conducted research revealed the following interesting fact: the participants of conciliation commissions and other organizations whose activities should be aimed at strengthening the family, had a very vague idea of what their responsibilities were!

But divorce is not only a personal tragedy of two people, but also a blow to their children. 61.2% of families (!) had children at the time of the breakup.

Conclusion. The conclusions given in the article are preliminary, and the data, although symptomatically important, are only from one area. And yet there is also some encouraging result: many divorcing (37.3%) wanted to save the family. But they did not succeed. The reason is the contradiction between the persisting traditional ideas about marriage (including the corresponding relationships in the family) and the formation of new value orientations of the young in their vision of the future family. And we must understand that in the 21st century, traditional marriage will inevitably fall apart. Everything flows, everything changes. And our task is not only to realize this, but also to do everything so that the negative consequences of the birth of a new family model are minimized and less dramatic. Behind each such drama are the destinies of people.

References:

1. Современный словарь иностранных слов / под ред. И. В. Нечаева. – М. : АСТ, 2002. – 538 с.
2. Веселова, Е. К. Психологическая деонтология: автореф. дис. ... д-ра психол. наук / Е. К. Веселова. – СПб.: СПбГУ, 2003. – 45 с.
3. Краткая философская энциклопедия. – М.: Прогресс; Энциклопедия, 1994.
4. Филатова, И. А. Деонтологическая подготовка педагогов-дефектологов в условиях современного образования [Электронный ресурс]: автореф. дис. ... д-ра пед. наук / И. А. Филатова.